

Comparisons between the Deaf experts' decisions and the literature regarding the characteristics of SASL, cognition of Deaf people, and multimedia learning

Analysis of scripts and narrations in SASL

The decisions from the Deaf experts for the scripts and narrations touched upon the characteristics of SASL, cognition of Deaf learners, and multimedia learning.

Characteristics of SASL	The Deaf experts' decisions
3) Lexicon+ 1) Phonology	√ The team used these characteristics for newly invented signs: diabetes, cell, energy, blood pressure, and heart disease
4) Other signed languages	√ The team referred to other sign languages, if available, before inventing new signs in SASL
5) Invented iconic signs+ 2) Morphology	√ The team used these characteristics for newly invented signs: glucose, insulin, insulin injection, and cholesterol
6) Fingerspelling	√ The team used this characteristic as part of new sign for pancreas and kidney
7) Discourse structure	√
8) Syntax structure	√

Characteristics of cognition of Deaf learners	The Deaf experts' decisions
1) Signed language is an effective language	√ SASL is used for the narration.
2) Pieces of information should be chunked	√ They rearranged the scripts, plus merging some of them together. Fundamental knowledge of how our body gets energy (former Content 2) and relationship of insulin, blood glucose, and body cells (former Content 3) were merged as how the human body gets energy (the current Content 2). How the disease progresses and causes complications (former Content 5) and risk factors of becoming diabetics (former Content 6) were merged as why people become diabetic (the current Content 4).
3) Visual modality is important	- (This is part of visual materials)
4) Dynamic visual displays are helpful	- (This is part of visual materials)
5) Strong at attention shifting and detecting of motion in the periphery	- (This is part of the presentation on SASL narrations, the visual material, subtitles, and voice)
6) Multimodal information is advantageous but should not consecutively alternating of Deaf people's attention as it might impede their learning	- (This is part of the presentation on SASL narrations, the visual material, subtitles, and voice)

Characteristics of multimedia learning	The Deaf experts' decisions
1) Multimedia	- (This is part of the presentation on SASL narrations, the visual material, subtitles, and voice)
2) Spatial contiguity	- (This is part of the presentation on SASL narrations, the visual material, subtitles, and voice)
3) Temporary contiguity	- (This is part of the presentation on SASL narrations, the visual material, subtitles, and voice)
4) Coherence	! Irrelevant words, pictures, and sounds were excluded. However, extensive elaborations, for matching the understandability of the Deaf viewers with different backgrounds, may contradict this characteristic.
5) Modality	- (This is part of the presentation on SASL narrations, the visual material, subtitles, and voice)
6) Redundancy	- (This is part of the presentation on SASL narrations, the visual material, subtitles, and voice)
7) Pretraining	√ For the interactive video (the current Content 4), a guide on how to interact with the interactive video was provided.
8) Signaling	√ The signalling was given during a kind of elaboration messages that introduce the content of each video.
9) Personalization principle	√ This is in-line with how SASL is communicated. "You" and "your" are used as part of the narrations.

Analysis of visual materials

The decisions from the Deaf experts for visual materials touched upon the characteristics of cognition of Deaf learners.

Characteristics of cognition of Deaf learners	The Deaf experts' decisions
1) Signed language is an effective language	- (This is part of the scripts and narrations in SASL)
2) Pieces of information should be chunked	- (This is part of the scripts and narrations in SASL)
3) Visual modality is important	√ Visual modality was applied to the current Contents 2, 3, and 4 that present non-simple contents.
4) Dynamic visual displays are helpful	√ Animation was applied to the current Content 2 since it describes the disease progression in the body better than illustrations.
5) Strong at attention shifting and detecting of motion in the periphery	- (This is part of the presentation on SASL narrations, the visual material, subtitles, and voice)
6) Multimodal information is advantageous but should not consecutively alternating of Deaf people's attention as it might impede their learning	- (This is part of the presentation on SASL narrations, the visual material, subtitles, and voice)

Analysis on the presentation of SASL narrations, the visual material, subtitles, and voice

The decisions from the Deaf experts for the scripts and narrations touched upon the characteristics of cognition of Deaf learners and multimedia learning.

Characteristics of cognition of Deaf learners	The Deaf experts' decisions
1) Signed language is an effective language	√ (as stated beforehand)
2) Pieces of information should be chunked	√ (as stated beforehand)
3) Visual modality is important	√ (as stated beforehand)
4) Dynamic visual displays are helpful	√ (as stated beforehand)
5) Strong at attention shifting and detecting of motion in the periphery	√! They argued with the author's proposal on pausing narration in SASL and subtitle for presenting animation or each illustration. They recommended to display narration, a visual material, and subtitle at the same time because Deaf people are strong at shifting their attention among these three components.
6) Multimodal information is advantageous but should not consecutively alternating of Deaf people's attention as it might impede their learning	

Characteristics of multimedia learning	The Deaf experts' decisions
1) Multimedia	! This characteristic is not directly applicable to the learning of Deaf people. They mainly process information through the visual channel. Only a few Deaf people, plus their hearing significant others, need to process information via the auditory channel, in addition to the visual channel.
2) Spatial contiguity	√ They decided to put the subtitles at the bottom of each video
3) Temporary contiguity	√ This characteristic was applied for the current Content 2, which its contents are the most sophisticated in comparison to other videos.
4) Coherence	√
5) Modality	√ The decisions of the Deaf experts were partially in-line with this characteristic because they agreed that narration in SASL, a visual material, subtitles, and voice should be displayed, altogether.
6) Redundancy	X This characteristic contradicted Deaf people's learning on multimedia learning. (see the reason above).
7) Pretraining	- (This is part of the scripts and narrations in SASL)
8) Signaling	- (This is part of the scripts and narrations in SASL)
9) Personalization principle	- (This is part of the scripts and narrations in SASL)